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Guardians of the Fuel Cells: An Automated Monitoring Framework with Digital Twins

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Abstract

The challenging durability targets for fuel cells, reaching up to 25,000 h, require precise monitoring to ensure slow aging and to prevent damage. As open systems, fuel cells are susceptible not only to internal faults but also to harmful external influences, such as contamination. Since cell voltage is a sensitive indicator for the fuel cell’s state of health, we have presented a digital twin-based monitoring approach to detect anomalous events based on cell voltage [1].

To automate this approach, we present a novel web-based framework for automated fuel cell monitoring. This framework builds on the developed fuel cell digital twin models and enables the automated application of these models. A web-based graphical user interface allows the user to create and train a digital twin for a new fuel cell. After training the model, the framework uses this digital twin to monitor new measurement data in real time.

As shown in Figure 1, the lifecycle of a digital twin in the framework consists of three steps. First, the framework uses a pre-trained digital twin and trains it on the specifics of each new fuel cell using transfer learning. Since a pre-trained model is used, only a few data points (< 100) are required. Second, the transferred model is used to check new measurement data in real time. If anomalies are detected, a notification is sent to the user via an email notification service. After a defined period of time (e.g. every second week), the digital twin is retrained using past data. This allows the model's predictive accuracy to improve over time. The retrained model is then used for data monitoring.

Figure 1. Digital Twin Lifecycle

Introduction

Continuous monitoring helps to maximize the lifetime of fuel cells and thus achieve the durability targets of up to 25,000 h for heavy-duty applications. In [1] we presented a set of methods for monitoring the operation of fuel cells using artificial intelligence (AI). Due to the availability of data from the application of fuel cells in real systems, the demonstrations were limited to the operation of fuel cells on test stations. It has been shown that a distinction must be made between monitoring the test station and monitoring the fuel cell. The test station can be monitored using simple statistical methods such as the Gaussian 3-sigma rule. The fuel cell, on the other hand, can be monitored using a digital twin that calculates a prediction for the cell voltage based on the current and past operating conditions of the fuel cell. By comparing the predicted and measured cell voltage, anomalies can be identified as deviations between the two. This approach allows disentangling the various influences on the cell voltage (i.e. operating conditions, temporal effects such as reversible and irreversible cell voltage degradation, reactant quality, defects, ...) and thus identifying the presence of anomalous influences.

A second generation of the AI-based digital twin was presented in [2] as a combination of a stationary fuel cell model and a degradation model to overcome the identified limitations of the first generation. The development and validation of the stationary fuel cell model was reported in [3], while the degradation model was presented in [4]. To use this approach for automated fuel cell monitoring, a framework was proposed in [2] that automatically trains and applies the AI models to new fuel cell data. This article presents a prototype version of this framework for automated fuel cell monitoring.

1. Design & Architecture

As proposed in [2], the automated monitoring framework is built in a service based software architecture. Therefore, "several well-established open source software tools that are orchestrated by small Python scripts [are used]. Since a large community maintains the software tools, only the small Python scripts need to be developed and maintained." [2]. In contrast to a monolithic application, this allows to reduce the maintenance effort and to logically structure the code. Figure 2 shows the five different services of the framework and their interconnection.

Figure 2. Monitoring framework services. "A web-based *streamlit* user interface allows editing the monitoring configurations stored in a MongoDB. The prefect based task scheduler then uses these configurations to train and run models stored in the model registry." [2]

Monitoring Configuration

A *monitoring configuration* is the key concept in the automation framework. This configuration, with a predefined and validated schema, is stored in the *Config Store*, a MongoDB document database. It contains all relevant information for a single monitoring task, including

- **metadata:** name, description, creation and modification timestamps
- **data pre-processing steps:** data source, parameters, mutations, aggregations, step detection, filters
- **algorithm settings:** algorithm type, parameters
- **notification settings:** contact names or groups
- **monitoring settings:** retraining interval, monitoring interval

Graphical User Interface

“A web-based [GUI] based on the Python package *streamlit* provides an easy way to access and edit monitoring configurations through graphical windows and dialogs as shown in figure 4” [2]. It provides an easily accessible graphical way to define the queries to prepare the data for monitoring. This includes arithmetic operations to calculate new parameters based on one or more input parameters, aggregations such as summation or averaging, step detection based on a given parameter, or windowing by a time range. Internally, the graphical queries are translated into SQL and sent to the database. In addition, all other contents of the monitoring configuration can be edited. The object-oriented implementation of the monitoring configuration and the GUI allow a quick and easy extension of the framework with new monitoring algorithms or pre-processing steps.

Besides editing the configuration, the GUI provides access to all the services shown in figure 2 including the *Task Scheduler* and the *Model Registry*. New tasks can be submitted to the scheduler with just a few clicks, while the progress of running tasks is visualized. Completed task runs, such as training or monitoring runs, can be inspected using a set of tools. This allows the user to check the prediction accuracy of a model or find the root cause of an anomaly detection. In addition, models stored in the model registry can be inspected as shown in figure 7 to help identify the causes of false classifications. For example, training metrics such as RMSE of neural networks or the resulting feature importance can be visualized.

Database

The *MariaDB* database stores the measurement data from the fuel cells on the test stations. A real time data streaming pipeline [2] is used to transfer new measurement data into the database. The data is stored with a proper structure and can be later queried using the query language SQL.

Model Registry

The Model Registry based on the Python software *mlflow*, is responsible for versioning the trained models and archiving the training metrics. During the training of new models, metrics such as RMSE or Negative log-likelihood are tracked by mlflow and can be visualized in the GUI. "Once training is complete, the trained model is stored in the model registry" [2] and added to version control. This allows reverting to previous model versions or reusing older versions for new monitoring tasks. The latest model can be retrieved to check new data for anomalies.

Task Scheduler

"The task scheduler, using the Python package *prefect*, is the central component of the framework and responsible for all heavy workloads. Triggered by a schedule or manually via the GUI, the scheduler trains models or applies models to check new data [...] by executing a set of Python functions on a dedicated server that is connected to all services." [2] This separation facilitates the maintenance and development of the framework since each service and each task is responsible for a precisely defined set of tasks compared to a monolithic software application that handles all tasks.

2. Prototype

The prototype of the automated fuel cell monitoring framework is designed as a web-based application to provide a user-friendly interface for managing and executing monitoring tasks. This section elaborates on the key components and functionalities of the prototype, providing a comprehensive overview of its operation.

The home page, as shown in figure 3, acts as the central hub for users to begin their monitoring activities. Upon accessing the application, users are presented with a list of existing monitoring configurations. Each configuration represents a specific setup for monitoring a particular fuel cell or test scenario. Users must select an appropriate configuration from this list before proceeding to any other section of the application. This selection is crucial as it sets the context for all subsequent actions, ensuring that the user is working with the correct parameters and settings. The home page's design emphasizes clarity and ease of navigation, streamlining the initial steps of the monitoring workflow.

Figure 3. The home page provides an overview on the available monitoring configuration and serves as the entry point of the web application. A configuration to work with on all further pages must be selected on this page.

Once a configuration is chosen or newly created, the user interacts with the configuration editor as depicted in figure 4 to define the specifics of the monitoring process. A key feature of this editor is its graphical interface, which abstracts the complexity of database queries. Instead of writing SQL code directly, users can visually construct queries using a form-based approach. This "no-code" environment allows for a broader range of users, including those without extensive database knowledge, to effectively set up monitoring parameters. The interface supports various data manipulation operations, including standard arithmetic calculations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division), data aggregation functions (e.g.,

calculating the mean or sum of data points), and the ability to assign alias names to data fields for clarity. Behind the scenes, the application translates these graphical specifications into optimized SQL queries that are executed in the database. This translation is hidden from the user, who can focus on defining the logic of the monitoring task.

Configuration Editor

The screenshot shows the 'Configuration Editor' interface. At the top, there is a 'General Settings' tab. Below it, the 'Data' section is expanded, showing a list of 'Parameters'. The first parameter is 'Mean of 'p.Si.A.err [barg]'' with a 'Type' of 'Aggregation' and an 'Operation' of 'Mean'. The second parameter is 'p.Si.A [barg] - p.S.A.set [barg] as p.Si.A.err [barg]' with a 'Type' of 'Arithmetic' and an 'Operation' of 'Subtract'. This parameter is broken down into two sub-parameters: 'Minuend: Select 'p.Si.A [barg]' as 'p.Si.A [barg]'' with a 'Type' of 'Selection' and 'Parameter' of 'p.Si.A [barg]', and 'Subtrahend: Select 'p.S.A.set [barg]' as 'p.S.A.set [barg]'' with a 'Type' of 'Selection' and 'Parameter' of 'p.S.A.set [barg]'. Both sub-parameters have an 'Alias' field set to their respective parameter names. At the bottom of the configuration area, there are two buttons: 'Remove Parameter' (red) and 'Duplicate Parameter' (blue).

Figure 4. After a configuration is selected or created, the configuration can be edited in the configuration editor. A graphical interface provides a no-code interface to define the database queries including arithmetic operations (addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division), aggregations (mean, sum) and the definition of alias names. After saving, the back-end then converts this configuration into the corresponding database queries.

Configuration Editor

🔧 General Settings ▼

📊 Data ▼

👁️ Monitoring ▲

🔄 Retrain Interval 🔗

Days
 - + 🔗

Hours
 - + 🔗

Minutes
 - + 🔗

🕒 Backlog 🔗

Days
 - + 🔗

Hours
 - + 🔗

Minutes
 - + 🔗

🔍 Check Interval 🔗

Days
 - + 🔗

Hours
 - + 🔗

Minutes
 - + 🔗

🧠 Method 🔗

🧠 Gaussian ▼

🧠 Gaussian ▲

Group By 🔗

Choose an option ▼

Number of Sigmas 🔗

5 - +

+ Add Threshold

📧 Notification ▼

📄 Save

Figure 5. The type and the parameters of the monitoring algorithm can be edited in the monitoring section of the configuration editor. This includes algorithm specific options but also trainings specific options such as the retrain interval.

The monitoring section of the configuration editor, illustrated in figure 5, is where users define and configure the methods for fuel cell monitoring. This involves selecting the type of monitoring algorithm to be employed (e.g., a specific type of digital twin model) and setting the algorithm's parameters. These parameters are crucial for tailoring the algorithm's behavior to the specific characteristics of the fuel cell under observation. Furthermore, this section allows users to specify training-related options, such as the retrain interval. The retrain interval determines how frequently the monitoring model is updated with new data. Regular retraining is essential to maintain the model's accuracy and adapt to changes in the fuel cell's performance over time.

With the configuration fully defined, the *training* page shown in figure 6 is used to initiate the model training process. This is where the digital twin model learns from historical data to establish a baseline for normal fuel cell operation. The training process is a critical step, and the training page provides users with valuable feedback. It displays key training parameters, such as the start and end timestamps of the data used for training, giving users a clear understanding of the data's scope. Additionally, the page reports any warnings or errors that occurred during the training run. These warnings are crucial for diagnosing potential issues and ensuring the model's reliability. The training process itself is executed in the background as a job in the task scheduler that provides the required computational power for the training. The information shown on the training page is queried from the task scheduler.

Trainings

Start Time (UTC)	State	Total Run Time	Data Start Time (UTC)	Data End Time (UTC)
2025-03-27 14:45:49	✓ Completed	2 minutes	2024-11-12 23:00:10	2025-03-20 13:26:24
2025-03-11 12:23:03	✓ Completed	2 minutes	2024-11-12 23:00:10	2025-03-03 22:24:34

Details

Training Run

Start Time (UTC) ⓘ	End Time (UTC) ⓘ	Total Run Time ⓘ	Run State ⓘ
2025-03-27 14:45:49	2025-03-27 14:47:40	1 minute and 52 seconds	✓ Completed

State Message ⓘ

✓ Run completed without errors.

Model

Data Start Time (UTC) ⓘ	Data End Time (UTC) ⓘ	Data Length ⓘ	Model Status ⓘ
2024-11-12 23:00:10	2025-03-20 13:00:14	4 months, 5 days, 14 hours and 0 minutes	✓ FINISHED

Model Version ⓘ

4 (latest model)

[Go To Model](#)

[New Training](#)

Figure 6. After the configuration is completed, the training page allows running the first training. For finished trainings, the page provides an overview on the training parameters such as data start and end timestamp and shows warnings that have been encountered during the training run.

Upon successful completion of the training, the trained model is stored in the model registry. The *models* page as depicted in figure 7 serves as a repository for these trained models, providing a centralized location for managing and accessing them. The models page lists all available models, allowing users to browse and select the appropriate one for their monitoring needs. Furthermore, it offers detailed insights into each model, including its specific parameters and performance metrics. These metrics, such as RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error), provide a quantitative measure of the model's accuracy and reliability. Figure 7 specifically highlights a Gaussian model used for cyclic monitoring, and the visualization of the corresponding model parameters.

Figure 8 provides another perspective on the model page, focusing on a polynomial model used for a specific monitoring task: analyzing the relationship between coolant flow and pressure drop. This highlights the framework's ability to handle different model types and monitoring scenarios. The page displays the model's parameters, which define the shape of the polynomial function, and relevant performance metrics, allowing users to assess the model's fit and predictive power for this particular application.

Figure 7. A successful training run registers the trained model in the model registry. The models page lists the available models and provides a deep insight into the model parameters and the relevant metrics. This example shows a Gaussian model for cyclic monitoring.

 Models

Version	Stage	Status	Created (UTC)	Last Updated (UTC)
4	Production	READY	2025-03-27 14:47:40	2025-03-27 14:47:40
3	Archived	READY	2025-03-11 12:24:39	2025-03-11 12:24:39
2	Archived	READY	2025-03-11 10:55:40	2025-03-11 10:55:40
1	Archived	READY	2025-03-11 10:44:43	2025-03-11 10:44:43

Delete Model

General Model Information

Data Start Time (UTC) ⓘ	Data End Time (UTC) ⓘ	MLflow Run Name ⓘ	Model Status ⓘ
2024-11-12 23:00:10	2025-03-20 13:00:14	upset-crane-288	FINISHED

Model Parameters

Coefficients ⓘ	Standard Deviation ⓘ
x^0 : 0.004	0.004
x^1 : 0.017	
x^2 : -0.020	

Figure 8. Overview on the model parameters and metrics for a polynomial model that is used to monitor the correlation of coolant flow and pressure drop.

The core function of the framework is to apply the trained models to incoming, real-time measurement data from the fuel cells. The task scheduler executes this process in the background, governed by a schedule defined in the monitoring configuration. The monitoring *runs* page shown in figure 9 provides an overview of these monitoring activities, listing each run and its associated details. This includes timestamps, input data ranges, and, most importantly, any alerts that were triggered by the model. Alerts indicate deviations from the expected behavior, signaling potential anomalies or faults in the fuel cell's operation.

To ensure timely responses to detected anomalies, the framework includes a notification system. Figure 10 shows the notification settings, where users can specify who should receive alerts. This involves defining individual recipients or creating alerting groups, allowing for flexible and targeted communication. The ability to define groups is particularly useful for larger teams, ensuring that the right personnel is informed based on their roles and responsibilities.

Figure 9. The trained models are applied to new data on a regular basis as defined in the monitoring configuration. This page lists the different monitoring runs for the selected configuration including the run details and the raised alerts.

When a monitoring run detects an anomaly that exceeds predefined thresholds, the system automatically sends out an alert notification via email to the designated recipients as shown in figure 11. This proactive approach ensures that stakeholders are immediately aware of any potential issues, enabling them to take prompt corrective actions. Furthermore, the system is designed to send out clearing notifications. If a subsequent monitoring run does not detect the anomaly, a clearing notification is automatically sent out to inform recipients that the situation has returned to normal. This feature helps to reduce alarm fatigue and ensures that users are only alerted to genuine and persistent problems.

Notification Settings

[? Help](#)

[Recipients](#) [Groups](#)

Name	E-Mail Address	Notification Groups
[Redacted]	[Redacted]@zsw-bw.de	
[Redacted]	[Redacted]@zsw-bw.de	
[Redacted]	[Redacted]@zsw-bw.de	[Redacted]
[Redacted]	[Redacted]@zsw-bw.de	

Name: [Redacted] Group: Choose an option [Save](#)

Figure 10. The recipients of alert notifications including alerting groups can be defined and edited in the notification settings.

 1 firing alerts

[View in StackAlert](#)

Configuration

Testbench: TST06
Stack ID: [Redacted]
Name: Slow Control

Details

Check Timestamp: 2025-03-29 22:34:58
Data Start: 2025-03-29 11:34:21
Data End: 2025-03-29 22:32:06

2025-03-29 18:48:28
Value of 'T.Si.C.err [°C]' (-6.617) for grouping value 402 is out of range (-6.555 - -2.352)

This email was automatically generated by StackAlert.

Figure 11. If a monitoring run raises an alert, a notification email is automatically sent out to the defined recipients. If a subsequent run does not raise any error, a clearing notification is sent out.

3. Conclusion

This article presented a prototype of a novel web-based framework designed to automate fuel cell monitoring using digital twin models. The framework streamlines the entire monitoring process, from model training to real-time anomaly detection and notification. A key feature is its user-friendly graphical interface, which simplifies the creation and configuration of monitoring tasks, enabling users to define complex data queries and algorithm parameters without requiring in-depth programming knowledge.

The prototype demonstrates the feasibility of automating the application of digital twin models for fuel cell monitoring. By integrating tools for data management, model training, task scheduling, and alert notifications, the framework provides a comprehensive solution for ensuring the longevity and safe operation of fuel cell systems.

Future work will focus on further testing and expanding the framework's capabilities by incorporating a wider range of monitoring algorithms and enhancing its scalability to handle larger datasets and more complex monitoring scenarios. In addition, a tool set for selecting time ranges of data that must be excluded from future trainings needs to be added.

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Declaration on the Use of Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Google Gemini (version 2.0, <https://gemini.google.com>) and DeepL Write (<https://www.deepl.com/de/write>) for wording suggestions and to improve the writing quality. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed. The authors take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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